

DEVELOPING ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC COMPETENCE IN THE EDUCATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FINE ARTS IN TRADITIONAL AND FOLK ART

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of developing artistic and aesthetic competence for future art teachers, with a focus on traditional and folk art in Uzbekistan. It highlights the communal nature of traditional art and its role in shaping individuality and creative expression. The document emphasizes the need for teachers to update and integrate students' knowledge, describe the emotional impact of art, and acquaint students with the importance of national culture. It also emphasizes the interconnectedness of artistic and aesthetic competence and professional competence, and the importance of engaging in artistic and creative activities for aesthetic development.*

Keywords: *composition, form, color, traditional art, folk art, artistic values, creative expression, aesthetic development, national culture, analyzing, evaluating, emotional impact, artistic interpretation, visual memory, artistic knowledge, workshops, exhibitions.*

Introduction. In our country, the material-technical base for the development of entrepreneurship, visual arts, folk applied arts, and craftsmanship has been established based on legal foundations. By educating and engaging women and girls in entrepreneurship and increasing the efficiency of labor resources through their involvement in business activities, opportunities have been created to broaden their entrepreneurial competencies through didactic and technological means as a result of them finding their places in society. Prominent tasks have been set for the comprehensive preservation and expansion of the cultural heritage and historical traditions of the Uzbek people, further development of national craftsmanship, folk arts, and practical arts, and the all-around support of citizens engaged in craftsmanship activities.

This text discusses the importance of training individuals in entrepreneurship, visual arts, folk applied arts, and craftsmanship in Uzbekistan, as well as the preservation and development of the nation's cultural and historical heritage. It also emphasizes the significance of promoting the competencies of women and girls in entrepreneurship and their active involvement in various business activities, with the goal of increasing their contributions to society. The text highlights the role of these efforts in preserving and expanding Uzbekistan's cultural and historical traditions, promoting national craftsmanship, and supporting citizens involved in craftsmanship activities. Contemporary traditional and folk art in Uzbekistan is experiencing a high level of development and success. Its progress and development is due to unique creative ideas and the growth of the public life environment.

Methodology. The shining stars of Uzbekistan's traditional art reach back to the ancient and rich layers of history. For centuries, due to the prevailing historical conditions, the people's traditional art remained the main type of visual art. The continuation of these traditions and the preservation of local uniqueness are the result of the complex ethnic history and the development of distinct schools in Central Asia.

This art is closely related to the people's way of life and is the most public form of art. Its communal nature allowed for a wide range of creative expression, which contributed to a strong

sense of individuality. Traditional art, along with oral poetry, was an important part of the people's spiritual culture and their expressions of thought, emotion, and the aesthetic appreciation of life. All art has contributed to a worldview that affirms human life.

The history of humanity is a history of cultural development, because human beings are separated from the animal world by culture. The development of culture is accompanied by the development of cultural ideas.

The history of cultural ideas has its own dynamics and unique stages of development. We obtain the oldest information about human culture from the oldest material sources. The primitive tools made of stone, metals, weapons, and other attributes of ancient life enable us to create a general picture of the lifestyle of our ancestors. These initial attributes of daily life created by humans are not only material but also a result of the cultural development of humanity. The oldest attributes of ancient life are not just the result of hard work, but also the product of the human intellect and cultural progress. During the period of the rise of national self-awareness and the establishment of sovereign national statehood, in conditions where peoples determine their own destiny, there is a growing interest among people in their own history, cultural heritage, and traditional customs. Culture cannot be ignored as a traditional aspect of national culture.

The object and methods of research were studied as the basis of practical art of the Uzbek people to shape the artistic and aesthetic competence of future teachers of fine arts. Competence is an essential part of the professional skill of future teachers of practical art. In the system for shaping the artistic and aesthetic competence of future teachers of practical arts, artistic craftsmanship occupies a suitable place.

Analysis and results. In literary art, students study Uzbek folk art works by analyzing and evaluating them through concepts of composition, form, and color. Through meetings with folk artists and craftsmen, there is a direct connection between individuals and society, which leads to the assimilation of their artistic values, requirements, and evaluations. This allows for a specific quality of change in artistic expression related to the micro-environmental changes within human life. This not only adds new valuable knowledge but also contributes to personal growth. Familiarizing oneself with various forms of practical arts through descriptive sources, observation, artistic interpretation, visual memory, and artistic knowledge, provides the opportunity to understand art works. Therefore, it is very important to approach art with responsible attitude and need, as it is not just a material need but also a means of obtaining knowledge - a way of understanding. In the process of education, students need to develop the skills of analyzing and evaluating works of art, using the concepts of composition, form, and color perception. Communication with folk artists and craftsmen during workshops and exhibitions plays an important role in establishing a direct relationship between the individual and society in the field of fine arts, incorporating its artistic principles, requirements, and evaluations into oneself. This allows for certain qualitative changes in the artistic field to reflect changes in the micro-environment of human life. This not only enriches the knowledge base but also contributes to the personal development of an individual.

To understand the conceptual nature of works of art in a sensory-aesthetic way and analyze the specific characteristics of their unique artistic forms, students require certain skills, expertise, and motivation. In pedagogical practice, it is necessary to provide students with a specific training to develop their skills of understanding and appreciating the beauty and appropriateness of created works. The teacher's understanding of the aesthetic characteristics of the object is conveyed

through their approach, and future teachers' preferences for certain aesthetic perspectives are also developed. Teachers need to demonstrate and highlight the three main aspects of their actions: a) To update and integrate students' knowledge and understanding of new concepts necessary for adequate perception and understanding of works of art; b) To describe the character of the emotional influence of the object on the observer.

In order to develop an aesthetic attitude towards the object in students, it is necessary for future teachers to draw on their experience in various fields. In mastering new materials, the principle of accuracy and consistency in logically connecting the various elements of the material, as well as the development of knowledge, skills and abilities in a certain order, should be required. It is also necessary to acquaint students with the importance of national culture, not only through their familiarity with the way of life and worldview of the Uzbek people, but also by discussing and developing issues related to these topics, opinions, beliefs, and ideals. Positive feelings and emotions are the basis for the development of interest in national culture.

In the lessons on painting and composition, the task is to increase the student's confidence in their own abilities through the effective use of artistic skills and knowledge. The teacher of the future should not only possess knowledge and skills recognized by tradition, but also have the ability to use the already established means of decorative art in order to create new models of personal activity and effective actions.

Artistic and aesthetic competence allows a person to understand their concepts related to artistic expression, develop their skills in this art, and understand the visual art techniques that impact them or that they can use to express themselves. This helps students to understand, analyze, and express their ideas on visual art, and learn to use various artistic techniques in practice.

Artistic and aesthetic competence enables students to acquire knowledge and skills in artistic expression, communicate their ideas effectively, create objective images, shapes, and compositions, and develop their own style. Additionally, artistic and aesthetic competence helps students to develop their creative thinking and express their imaginative ideas.

Professional competence helps students to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to perform their professional activities, gain practical experience and additional skills. Professional competence assists students in preparing for their professional activities and enables them to participate in their professional activities at a high level. This type of competence encompasses professional knowledge and skills, such as monitoring IT news in the IT field, solving mathematical problems, and acquiring social experience.

Conclusion. Artistic and aesthetic competence and professional competence have their own unique characteristics, and they must be interconnected and implemented together. Artistic and aesthetic competence helps individuals to understand visual art and express their emotions and needs, while professional competence helps them to use their knowledge and skills to participate in professional activities

The system of relationships identifies the nature of a person's experiences, their unique characteristics for understanding reality, and the character of their emotional reactions in relation to external influences. Artistic and aesthetic activity is one of the unique types of activity in human life, which develops a person's universal creative abilities and serves as a means of developing the person in all aspects. The aesthetic development of a person is related to constant communication with art and engagement in artistic and creative activities, as art is one of the social forms of human experience. Literary and creative activities, art, express a person's

aesthetic experience through an artistic representation that separates from reality with its independence and precision. The results of literary and creative activities are recorded both materially, as a product of the activity, and spiritually, in the experience of perceiving the world (as a special subjective form of reflecting reality, its defining feature is the ability to perceive chaotic events as the fact of life). In this context, we consider the "creation" method as a means of attracting literary and artistic activity teachers to creative activity, which is of great importance in future life directions. As a result, based on the understanding of art, a person creates their product at a certain point in time, distinguishing their individuality and uniqueness from the activities of others, and the world created by others is perceived, adapting to their living environment. It should be emphasized that in creating independent works, future visual art teachers need to rely on creativity, activity, purposefulness, and a multidimensional independent process. The personal qualities and activity of the student take a leading role in the process. It is important to note that this process involves active participation of both mental and intellectual processes. It ensures the involvement of all cognitive and intellectual processes.

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